

FACTORS IMPACT LEGALIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT PROMOTE STUDENT ON PROVINCIAL UNIVERSITY IN SICHUAN PROVINCE, CHINA

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Abstract

With the advancement of the strategy of law-based governance of the country and the deepening of campus legal construction, the legalization of educational management has become an important symbol and an inevitable choice for the modernization of contemporary universities. In this study, the legalization of educational management is selected as the research object, and the research objectives include: To study the level of legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province; To study levels of management of university students, legal system construction, university student rights relief influencing legalization of education management on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province; To investigate the causal factors of legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province; To proposal the development of legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province. In the course of the study, a combination of quantitative and qualitative analyses was used to select 540 people randomly among school administrators, educational administrators, full-time teachers, and legal advisors in 27 provincial universities in Sichuan Province, and a survey was conducted by means of a questionnaire. Finally 463 valid questionnaires were recovered. On the basis of collecting, organizing and analyzing the data from the recovered questionnaires using SPSS and AMOS, the SEM of legalization of education management was constructed. Subsequently, nine experts were invited to conduct a qualitative analysis study in the form of group interviews to confirm the model. The study found that, management of university students, legal system construction, university student rights relief and university student participation have a significant effect on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province. Management of university students, legal system construction and university student rights relief have a significant effect on university student participation. Management of university students, legal system construction and university student rights relief have an indirect impact on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province through university student participation. Finally, a model of the impact of management of university students, legal system construction, university student rights relief and university student participation on the legalisation of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province (Chi-square=5945.514, DF=4823, X²/DF=1.233, GFI=0.801, RMSEA=0.022, NFI=0.811, NNFI=0.957). This study helps to understand the overall status, effect factors and model promotion application of legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, and lays a certain theoretical foundation for related research on legalization of education management.

Keywords: Management of University Students, Legal System Construction, University Student Rights Relief, University Student Participation, Legalization of Education Management, Provincial Universities in Sichuan Province.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the advancement of the strategy of ruling the country according to law, the deepening of the construction of the campus of the rule of law and the enhancement of the awareness of the rights of college students, disputes and cases between college students and universities occur from time to time, which to a certain extent exposes the lack of the spirit of the rule of law in the management of college students.

Rule of law, rule of law campus need to achieve the rule of law of college students management, which is the need to enhance the legal awareness of teachers and students, but also an important symbol of the modernisation of college students management and the inevitable choice.

The full implementation of the rule of law is the basic way in which the Communist Party of China leads the people in the governance of the country, and it is a profound revolution in the governance of the country. Ruling the country according to law is the basic strategy of the Communist Party of China (CPC) in leading the people to govern the country, and it is a notable symbol of the progress of social civilisation and a necessary guarantee of the country's long-term peace and stability.

In 2014, the Fourth Plenary Session of the 18th CPC Central Committee made the Resolution of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China on a Number of Important Issues Concerning Comprehensively Promoting the Rule of Law in Compliance with the Law. The 19th CPC Central Committee National Congress of 2017 set up the Leading Group of the State of Comprehensively Governing the Country according to the Law to strengthen the unified leadership. In 2020, the Fifth Plenary Session of the 19th CPC Central Committee put forward new and higher requirements for comprehensively promoting the rule of law.

Xi Jinping pointed out that to promote the modernisation of the national governance system and governance capacity, it is necessary to adhere to the rule of law. Universities shoulder important functions and missions such as talent training, scientific research, social service, cultural inheritance and innovation, and international exchanges and cooperation, and should be at the forefront of the process of comprehensively promoting the rule of law. Strengthening university students' legal literacy work has become an inevitable requirement of the strategy of ruling the country according to law.

The legalization of university management requires the full participation of university students. According to Martin Trow's research on the three-stage theory of the development process of higher education, students have gradually possessed the right to influence decision-making in the internal governance of universities, and the form and degree of student participation has become an important issue during the period of transition of higher education from elitism to massification.

The Outline of the National Medium- and Long-Term Educational Reform and Development Plan (2010-2020) explicitly states that in the future governance of higher education in China, it is necessary to 'strengthen the construction of staff congresses and student congresses, and

give full play to the role of mass organization’, which provides a policy basis and jurisprudential foundation for students' participation in the internal governance of universities. In addition, the Interim Measures for the Formulation of Statutes of Higher Education Institutions issued by the Ministry of Education in 2011 clearly stipulates that the organisation and drafting of statutes should involve student representatives and fully reflect students' demands and wishes.

Modern university organisational activities show that students are not only one-way recipients of education, but also participants and supervisors of education, and that students and scholars share the responsibility for the quality and development of education (Feng & Ding, 2015, p. 20). Therefore, the democratic participation of college students in affairs related to their own education and management is both an effective measure to improve their self-education and self-management, and a basic requirement of existing laws and regulations.

Therefore, in the current social context, the study of the rule of law in the management of college students has important theoretical value and practical significance. We should actively explore the mode of rule of law in the management of college students, improve the effectiveness of ideological and political education, and promote the development of higher education and the overall development of college students.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The researcher uses relevant concepts, theories and related research to combine various information and important content as a guideline for research study.

Chen Baosheng, Minister of Education, pointed out in his speech at the 2018 ‘National Conference on the Legal System in Education’ that the field of education is an important area of the rule of law, and the comprehensive promotion of the rule of law in education is an unshirkable responsibility and mission of the education system, an urgent requirement for accelerating the modernisation of education and building a strong education nation, and a summary of the experience of the long-term reform and development of the education cause.

The 2020 National Conference on the Legal System in Universities pointed out that strengthening the rule of law in universities is a fundamental task for universities to implement the basic strategy of ruling the country in accordance with the law in an all-round way, a realistic need to improve the level of development of China's higher education and enhance the core competitiveness of the country, and an intrinsic requirement to cope with the change of the main contradictions in the field of higher education and to promote the cause of higher education..

Hou et al. (2022, P51) pointed out that the construction of the legalization of educational management is a process of continuous innovation and development, and the formation of a scientific legalized management system requires the construction of four mechanisms. The second is the implementation of supervision, evaluation and assessment mechanism construction.

The third is the construction of student assistance mechanism. The fourth is the construction of student self-management mechanism.

Li (2023, P18) defines student participation as students' participation as school stakeholders in the discussion and resolution of school affairs in the form of individuals or groups, student representatives, etc., including participation in school development planning and decision-making, teaching evaluation, logistic construction and services, etc., with the right to speak and make decisions.

According to 'Innovation of Student Affairs Management Models in Chinese Universities', student affairs management refers to the non-academic management activities of universities to promote the comprehensive, balanced and sustainable development of students by guiding, regulating and serving the growth process of students (Feng, 2019, P21).

Hou et al. (2022, P52) believe that the principle of combining management, legal system and service is a practical refinement and scientific generalization based on a full understanding of the internal and external laws of student management in universities and the laws of students' growth, which provides conditions and guarantees for enhancing the effectiveness of student management in universities.

Wang (2020, p37) points out that the effective establishment of a standardised three-dimensional system of legal norms at the national and local levels as well as in universities must be achieved by constructing a three-dimensional system of laws and legal norms at the national, local and university levels, while also adhering to the unity of the principle of the rule of law, and making sure to ensure that the process of formulating subordinate laws refers to the superior laws.

Hu (2022, p135) has improved the relevant laws, regulations and management systems. Only when the laws and regulations, implementing rules and regulations complement each other, improve each other, and complement each other, the legal system is perfect and systematic, and there are clear and specific standards for the implementation of laws and regulations. This must also take into account the specific circumstances in the implementation and enforcement process, and formulate corresponding implementing rules and regulations for more effective implementation.

Yin and Wang (2021, p31) Broaden the way of students' rights. The ideal way to solve the infringement of students' rights and interests in management is to solve the problem within the school, where both parties can negotiate and reduce confrontation. Schools should set up independent and professional relief organisations and include some students to participate in the work.

Universities can introduce mediation, arbitration, conciliation and other non-litigation solutions in the process of student management, and refine the regulations to broaden the ways of relief for students' rights.

Yang (2022, p81) suggests that universities should establish a sound student aid system to guarantee the formality and legality of the aid pathway for college students, which is an important guarantee for universities to realise the rule of law management, and also an important basis to ensure that students' personal interests are not infringed upon. The principles of openness and transparency, universal participation and hearing system should be incorporated into the management of universities.

At the same time, educational arbitration bodies should be established and used as a coordinating medium for litigation between students and universities.

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Based on the research of related scholars, this paper proposes the following hypotheses and forms a conceptual model diagram for the study:

- H1: Management of university students has a significant effect on university student participation.
- H2: Management of university students has a significant effect on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China.
- H3: Legal system construction has a significant effect on university student participation.
- H4: Legal system construction has a significant effect on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China.
- H5: University student rights relief has a significant effect on university student participation.
- H6: University student rights relief has a significant effect on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China.
- H7: University student participation has a significant effect on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China.
- H8: Management of university students has an indirect impact on legalization of education management through university student participation.
- H9: Legal system construction has an indirect impact on legalization of education management through university student participation.
- H10: University student rights relief has an indirect impact on legalization of education management through university student participation.

Figure 1: conceptual model

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a mixed approach to research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative methods. The specific design is as follows:

Step 1 Investigates the current status of legalization of educational management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China, through literature review, expert interviews and content analysis.

Step 2.1 Analyze the relationship of factor management of university students, legal system construction, university student rights relief and university student participation influencing legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China, by a questionnaire to survey stakeholders.

Step 2.2 Create the model of university students, legal system construction, university student rights relief and university student participation influencing legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China.

Step 3 Inspect the model of management of university students, legal system construction, university student rights relief and university student participation influencing legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China, by focus group and content analysis.

Sample size of at least 20 times the size of the sample is required for structural equation modelling (SEM) using multivariate methods (Lindeman et al., 1980). Since there are 20 observable variables in this study, the minimum sample size should be $(20 \times 20) = 400$. Considering the recovery rate and validity of the follow-up questionnaires, Zhang and Han (2020) believe that the effective recovery rate of questionnaires can reach 70%-80%, and (Liu and Li, 2022) believe that the effective recovery rate of questionnaires can reach more than 90%, therefore, in order to ensure the stability of the data, the thesis enlarged the sample size by distributing 550 questionnaires. Finally, 463 valid questionnaires were recovered, and the effective recovery rate was 84.18%. The questionnaire data were collated and analysed for descriptive statistics, reliability and validity using SPSS and AMOS. The structural equation model of the influence of college students' management, legal construction, college students' rights relief and college students' participation on the legalisation of education management was established. And the hypotheses of this paper were verified by path analysis and intermediate effect test.

5. STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING

Based on previous research hypotheses, structural equation modelling was constructed, correlation lines between the independent variables were plotted, and the data were substituted into AMOS to produce the following results:

Figure 2: Structural Equation Modeling

Figure 2 shows a Structural Equation Model (SEM) that includes relationships between multiple latent and observed variables. The relationship between latent variables and observed variables: Each latent variable is measured by multiple observed variables, and the standard load coefficient (path coefficient) of these observed variables is above 0.7, indicating that the observed variable has a good measurement effect on the latent variable. Path relationship between latent variables: For example, IPE is correlated with WUSM by path coefficient 0.74, and DSM is correlated with MUS by path coefficient 0.57. These path relationships show causality and interaction between latent variables. Overall fit degree of the model: The fit index of the model (such as GFI, RMSEA, NFI and NNFI) shows that the model has a good fit degree, especially the RMSEA is 0.022, indicating that the error between the model and the data is small. The structural equation model shows the interaction and causality of various variables in detail through the path relationship between multiple latent variables and observed variables. The overall fit index of the model is good, indicating that the model can explain the underlying structure and relationship in the data well. In this way, many factors and influences such as management of university students, legal system construction, university student rights relief and university student participation can be more deeply understood.

Table 1: Structural equation model fitting index

Index	Judging standard	Statistical value	Fit condition
CMIN	-	5945.514	-
DF	-	4823	-
CMIN/DF	<3	1.233	Good
GFI	>0.90	0.801	Acceptable
RMSEA	<0.08	0.022	Good
NFI	>0.90	0.811	Acceptable
NNFI	>0.90	0.957	Good

Table 1 shows that the χ^2/df value is 1.233, which is less than 3. The RMSEA is 0.022, which is lower than the standard level 0.08, indicating a good fit. The GFI value was 0.801, and the NFI value was 0.811, which did not reach the standard of greater than 0.9, but reached the minimum standard of greater than 0.8, which was in the acceptable range. The NNFI value was 0.957, which reached the excellent standard. All the indicators of goodness of fit reached the acceptable standard, and the model fit was good.

Table 2: Hypotheses Testing Result of the Structural Model

Path	Non- standard load factor	S.E.	C.R.	P	Standardized load coefficient	Hypothesis
USP <--- MUS	0.554	0.095	5.842	***	0.554	H1
LEM <--- MUS	0.35	0.096	3.626	***	0.345	H2
USP <--- LSC	0.336	0.075	4.514	***	0.348	H3
LEM <--- LSC	0.195	0.071	2.749	0.006	0.199	H4
USP <--- USRR	0.15	0.045	3.308	***	0.211	H5
LEM <--- USRR	0.268	0.049	5.442	***	0.373	H6
LEM <--- USP	0.372	0.112	3.321	***	0.367	H7

Table 2 shows the test results of each path in the structural equation model. When $P < 0.05$ then the path is significant, and when the path is significant, the coefficient is positive then the independent variable has a significant positive effect on the dependent variable. The hypotheses (H1-H7) were statistically significant ($P < 0.01$). Specifically, Independent variable "Management of university students, Legal system construction, University student rights relief", and Intermediate variable "University student participation" had significant positive effects on Legalization of education management, indicating that the assumed path in the model was reasonable and expected.

6. INTERMEDIATE PATH CHECK

Using the bootstrap sampling method of AMOS 24, the mediated paths were examined using 5000 samples and the results are shown in the table below:

Table 3: The mediating Effect of University student participation on Management of university students and Legalization of educational management

Path	Type of effect	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P
Management of university students=>University student participation=>Legalization of educational management	Direct effect	0.35	0.075	0.647	0.019
	Indirect effect	0.206	0.069	0.47	0.006
	Total effect	0.556	0.368	0.788	0.000

Table 3 shows that Management of university students has significant direct and indirect effects on Legalization of educational Management. This means that Management of University students not only contributes directly to the Legalization of educational Management, but also enhances it through University student participation. The results support the key role of Management of University students and University student participation in promoting Legalization of educational Management.

Table 4: The mediating Effect of University student participation on Legal system construction and Legalization of educational management

Path	Type of effect	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P
Legal system construction=>University student participation=>Legalization of educational management	Direct effect	0.195	0.016	0.393	0.036
	Indirect effect	0.125	0.035	0.332	0.006
	Total effect	0.320	0.177	0.512	0.000

Table 4 shows that Legal system construction has significant direct and indirect effects on Legalization of educational management. This means that Legal system construction not only contributes directly to Legalization of educational management, but also enhances the impact by increasing University student participation. The results support the important role of Legal system construction and University student participation in promoting Legalization of educational management.

Table 5: The mediating Effect of University student participation on University student rights relief and Legalization of educational management

Path	Type of effect	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P
University student rights relief=>University student participation=>Legalization of educational management	Direct effect	0.268	0.147	0.419	0.001
	Indirect effect	0.056	0.008	0.16	0.015
	Total effect	0.324	0.206	0.465	0.000

Table 5 shows that the direct and indirect effects of university student rights relief on legalization of educational management are significant, and the total effects of both are also significant.

This means that university student rights relief not only contributes directly to the legalization of educational management, but also enhances that impact by increasing university student participation. The results support the important role of university student rights relief and university student participation in promoting legalization of educational management.

7. CONCLUSION

This article takes education management workers in provincial universities in Sichuan Province as the object of investigation, and adopts qualitative and quantitative research methods to study management of university students, legal system construction, university student rights relief and university student participation on the legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province.

Through qualitative research, information was gathered on the impact of management of university students, legal system construction, university student rights relief and university student participation on the information on the impact of legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, laying the foundation for future quantitative research. A quantitative research method was used for the survey and data collection.

Descriptive statistics, exploratory and validation factor analysis, and correlation analysis were conducted on 463 valid questionnaires, and structural equations were constructed using Excel, SPSS, and AMOS to analyse the collected data. These data were modelled to find out management of university students, legal system construction, university student rights relief and university student participation impacts on the legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province. Finally, the following conclusions were drawn:

Management of university students has a significant effect on university student participation. Management of university students has a significant effect on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China. Legal system construction has a significant effect on university student participation. Legal system construction has a significant effect on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China. University student rights relief has a significant effect on university student participation.

University student rights relief has a significant effect on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China. University student participation has a significant effect on legalization of education management in provincial universities in Sichuan Province, China. Management of university students has an indirect impact on legalization of education management through university student participation. Legal system construction has an indirect impact on legalization of education management through university student participation. University student rights relief has an indirect impact on legalization of education management through university student participation.

8. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

This paper can make a comparative study on the legalization of education administration between universities in Sichuan province and those in other provinces, analyze the differences and characteristics of the legalization of education administration in different regions, explore the reasons behind it, and provide more targeted suggestions for policy formulation.

Through the collection and analysis of historical data, this paper studies the evolution process of the rule of law in the education management of affiliated universities in Sichuan Province, understands its development context and stage characteristics, and provides historical experience and reference for the current and future reform

Combining the theories and methods of law, pedagogy, management and other disciplines, this paper makes a comprehensive analysis of the legalization of educational management, and probes into the interaction and influence between law, policy, management and educational practice.

Through empirical research methods such as questionnaire survey and in-depth interview, the opinions and suggestions of more front-line educators and students are collected to understand their cognition and expectation of the rule of law in education management, so as to provide more specific and realistic demand analysis for policy formulation.

The experience and practice of legalization of higher education management in other countries or regions can be compared to explore its enlightenment and reference significance to the legalization of higher education management in Sichuan Province.

This paper selects some typical cases of legalization of education management in Sichuan Province, analyzes their successful experience and problems, and provides examples for other universities to learn from.

This paper makes a long-term follow-up study on the legalization policy of education management, evaluates its effect and influence, and provides a basis for the continuous optimization and adjustment of the policy.

This paper discusses the role and responsibility of teachers and students in promoting the rule of law in education management, analyzes their participation degree and influence, and provides strategies for improving their awareness of rule of law and participation ability.

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